

Access, Interfaces, Data and Metadata

Report on scholarly needs for
WebData's data platform

WEBDATA

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WEBDATA

Access, Interfaces, Data and Metadata:

Report on scholarly needs for WebData's data platform

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Summary

The WebData project develops research infrastructure for the Norwegian web archive, funded by the Research Council of Norway (RCN). This needs study has mapped scholarly needs for a data platform through a survey (87 responses) and in-depth interviews (12 informants), focusing on four topics: *access*, *interfaces*, *data*, and *metadata*.

Access from the workplace is reported as crucial, especially for researchers at higher education campuses outside of Oslo. This appears to be decisive for whether the infrastructure is taken into use. There is also a consistent need for scalable reading – switching seamlessly between analysing big data and close reading individual documents – which requires good interoperability with NB’s replay service for the web archive.

Design must follow a “desktop first” principle, while mobile adaptation is not important. Browser-based access is important to all, while nearly half also want access via API and programming tools. Researchers ask in particular for search in full-text, advanced search syntax, filtering and faceting, as well as using results to define their own datasets and export search results.

Text content is very important for all scholars. Images and web pages as objects (replay) are also important to more than half of the respondents. Furthermore, there is a wish for speech transcription for audio and video, as well as various forms of search for image content. Content from public sector websites, news media, civil organisations, and scientific and non-scientific journals has the highest priority among those who responded.

Openly available metadata, such as a “table of contents” (CDX index), will be of value to many, independently of the research infrastructure. Researchers also want administrative and bibliographic metadata such as persistent links, publication title, estimated publication time and author name, as well as a number of more fine-grained needs for different media types. As far as possible, the project’s commitment to FAIR should be followed up with terms of access and information on licenses.

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1. Introduction

The WebData project is building a research infrastructure for the Norwegian web archive, with funding from the Research Council of Norway. The National Library of Norway (NB) has archived such data since the 1990s, and the material is in demand from scholars across a range of different fields. One of the project's four main goals is to:

Develop the infrastructure in close collaboration with the research community through needs and representation studies.

This report presents the results from a needs study that has examined the researchers' needs relating to WebData's data platform. The study was carried out in collaboration between NB, Humit at the University of Oslo (UiO) and Giellatekno at UiT The Arctic University of Norway.

Objective and approaches

The objective of this needs study is to identify scholarly needs related to the data platform. Needs have been mapped systematically within four topics: *access, interfaces, data* and *metadata*.

We want to understand the needs of a larger group of researchers, and at the same time obtain detailed knowledge of key stakeholders' needs. To do that, we have followed two different approaches:

1. A survey distributed broadly
2. Semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders.

The results should contribute to informed decisions and priorities for the development of the data platform (see Summary and recommendations, p. 10).

Data and privacy

All data were collected with active and informed consent, and processed in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

For privacy reasons, the collected raw data from individual responses were deleted by the end of the study, while aggregated results are compiled in a separate appendix to this report (Tønnessen, 2026).

2. Results from the survey

The survey was designed in line with Bethlehem & Biffignandis (2012, 237-283) roadmap for web surveys. This involves pre-testing, considering how the project is represented, and formulating instructions. The form was designed with logical branching, so that respondents only answered questions that were relevant to them. This was done both to ensure an increased completion rate and to ensure the quality of the results. For the same reason, respondents were given the option to answer “No opinion” on most questions.

A total of 87 responses were collected in the period 16.10.2025–05.02.2026. To ensure that responses came from relevant users (people who want to use the infrastructure), the survey was shared with a group that had already declared interest, as well as research communities focusing on digital methods and born-digital content (Tønnessen, 2026).

A broad range of disciplines

The respondents are primarily employed at universities and university colleges (UH). The humanities and social sciences are most represented, followed by computer science and education (figure 1). History, media studies, political science and linguistics are the disciplines with the most responses (figure 2).

A large share of the respondents teach students at bachelor’s, master’s and PhD programmes. Many want to use the infrastructure as part of teaching, where content from public sector websites and editor-controlled media (access categories 1 and 2) will be of great value.

Figure 2: Distribution by research area

Figure 1: Distribution by discipline

Interoperability for data platform and replay systems

Almost every respondent depends on access to some form of whole documents and metadata. This applies to both qualitatively and quantitatively oriented scholars. For the latter, this is partly about examining samples and understanding the context of aggregated data. As one of the informants put it in their interview:

When I work with statistics and short derivative snippets, it is important that I can easily jump into the document and see the context, and easily move back.

In practice, this means that the research infrastructure depends on the web archive’s replay services, and that there must be good interoperability between these and the WebData platform.

Access from workplace

Almost all respondents see it as important to have access from their workplace, which for many is a university campus. All respondents working outside Oslo answer that this is very important. This will probably be decisive to whether they start to use the infrastructure, and thus to what extent the research infrastructure can create value for its users.

«Desktop first»

When asked what kind of device they use for search, exploration and analysis, all respondents regard computers as very important. Only a very small share also wants access from a tablet or mobile phone. In contrast to the prevailing principle of “mobile first”, WebData’s interface must be designed according to a “desktop first” principle.

Browser for all, but many programmatic users

90,8% think browser-based interfaces are very important or fairly important. To nearly half of the respondents (44,8%), programmatic access through API and programmatic notebooks are also regarded as very or quite important.

Full-text search, scope data and export search results

Respondents think that the most important functions for search and exploration are full-text search, advanced search syntax, filtering, defining datasets and exporting references.

Text for everyone – images and replay for many

Text is an important media type to almost every respondent – including scholars who primarily research visual media. Important for many are also images, as well as ‘web pages as objects’, meaning the representation of multimodal objects as a unit itself. Among researchers concerned with audio and video, several report that they first and foremost long for speech transcription.

The most important content categories

More than 80% consider content from public sector websites to be very or quite important. News (online newspapers), webzines/non-scientific journals, as well as content from organisations and associations, also appear as important content categories to many.

Among the optional free-text responses, respondents reported interest in several other content categories: web-based art, literature blogs, political parties, as well as “meta-categories” such as link structures. The respondents should be taken into account when prioritising development, e.g. for enriching data. It should also be considered whether NB’s current web archiving satisfies the reported interests in various content categories, or if content collection could be improved.

Extraction of administrative and bibliographic metadata

The respondents have a strong desire for certain administrative and bibliographic metadata. This is information that does not exist in the web archive data today, and which – due to the scale of the archive – must be established automatically or semi-automatically.

Among the highest-priority wishes, persistent links – that is, a persistent identifier that can automatically be resolved to retrieve the archived object – appear as what is technically simplest to solve. At the same time, it requires anchoring in the organisation and collaboration to establish something durable over time.

Additionally, title of publication/website, name of creator, title of document and estimated time of publication are metadata that will be of great value to the respondents.

The large share of “no opinion” responses for identical or similar content indicates that many respondents are uncertain of what this means or how it can be used – both for scoping research data, and to reduce/increase noise in search results.

Terms of access and license

A large number of respondents are interested in the terms of access and licenses for reuse. With the project’s focus on the FAIR principles, one should look more closely into how this could be established or solved.

Metadata about content

Respondents were also asked about the importance of metadata about the content itself. There is a clear desire for metadata about language, formats (media subtypes), links and connections between documents/domain names, relations between resources and contextual information.

In the free-text responses, several highlighted the importance of metadata quality:

I only need metadata with good quality.

Where metadata is established automatically, some expressed a wish for information about the estimated quality of metadata, e.g. the confidence score of a classification.

For both audio and video, there is a desire to search in speech transcriptions. For images, there is a wish to search semantically, as well as to get information about the text that has surrounded an image. Some also expressed a wish for an estimate of whether the content is produced by generative AI tools or not.

3. Insights from interviews

A total of 12 informants contributed through interviews. The participants are regarded as key stakeholders in the WebData project, and have already expressed interest in utilising the research infrastructure and its data. Interviews were conducted as semi-structured conversations, following an interview guide with nine questions relating to the same topics as the survey (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, 46-47; Kvale & Brinkmann, 140-141). Unlike the survey responses, the interviews provide the opportunity to elaborate and reflect more in-depth, highlighting other aspects of key needs and obstacles.

Openly available metadata

Many of the interview informants emphasised the need for openly available metadata. This is crucial to scholars who, early on, need to decide if the archive's content is relevant to what they want to research. Apart from basic URL-based "table of contents" (CDX), many of them need additional administrative and bibliographic metadata (publication title, entity name, etc) to enable initial search and exploration.

Still, several of the key stakeholders asked for access to a simpler index and replay service. This would enable several types of research at the current stage, while waiting for more advanced systems for search and exploration, and is also fundamental for interoperability between the WebData platform and replay.

Faceting and filtering

The majority of informants pointed out that search interfaces should allow for refining or fine-tuning search. Faceting and filtration were mentioned by several as examples of valuable tools to refine search and allow them to scope results relevant to their interest.

Distant reading ⇔ Close reading

One of the informants formulated very precisely what several others touched upon:

When I work with statistics and short derivative snippets, it is important that I can easily jump into the document and see the context, and easily move back.

This is an important example of why interoperability between data platform and replay is crucial, because many scholars will be doing a kind of 'scalable reading', moving between statistics and empirical examples.

Transcribing speech

More than half of the informants have a desire to search for text in audio and video, expecting that they can search speech transcriptions the same way they search for regular text.

Source criticism of replay

Media scholars and historians who were interviewed were particularly clear about the need for source-critical tools when documents are replayed in a wayback machine:

«Internet Archive has a brilliant diff function that shows the time difference between when the HTML and other resources have been archived. This is crucial to assessing whether the replay is a probable version of the historic page, and to what extent one can trust the replayed page.»

Tools for network analysis

Among those who have already been using web archives in their research, network analysis of website/domain-name relations stood out as a highly valuable aspect of what web archives can offer to research.

Early testing

Almost all informants want early access to the platform, so that they can give feedback on functionality. Some also offered to contribute with feedback on “completeness”, that is, the extent to which harvesting has been broad or deep enough:

I have at times been disappointed by the scope and lack of depth in the collections of various archives. At the same time, I have experienced that input from researchers, such as myself, would help to improve the collection. So, I think it is essential that you open up and receive scholarly input in this area.

This is something that both the WebData project and NB’s web archive can benefit from, improving the archiving of web content and thus increasing the value and relevance of the infrastructure.

4. Summary and recommendations

The results from mapping researcher needs – with 87 survey responses and 12 in-depth interviews – provides a solid picture of scholarly users’ needs relating to the data platform. This should be used as a basis when making priorities and making decisions on development.

It is a fundamental need for **scalable reading** – that is, switching between statistical aggregates or analysis of big data and replay of individual pages (close reading ↔ distant reading). This applies to both qualitatively and quantitatively oriented scholars, meaning that the data platform must have good interoperability with the web archive’s replay service.

Equally important is **access from the scholars’ workplace**. This especially applies to those working on UH campuses outside of Oslo. Lacking access from there will largely limit the degree to which the infrastructure is taken into use.

For interfaces, the responses points unambiguously towards a “**desktop first**” principle. Everyone will benefit from good browser-based services, while a considerable share also wants programmatic access through API and notebooks.

The researchers need **powerful tools for search and exploration** – full-text search, syntax with logical operators, filtered search and results faceting, as well as the opportunity to define specific corpora, export search results and persistent identifiers to content. Text appears to be crucial across fields and research interests, while the need for image, audio and video is to some extent also tied to text content, including speech transcriptions.

There is a desire for **openly available metadata** (CDX) before more advanced systems are in place. The researchers also ask for administrative and bibliographic metadata that currently does not exist, such as persistent links, title of publication, link data, and much more. Considerable subgroups want tools for source criticism of playback, analysis of content and network analysis. Some of this exists in the technology used for the test platform, while other parts must be developed further by the project.

Two aspects cut across the themes and should be given consideration: first, the project’s anchoring in the FAIR principles should be followed up with persistent links, terms of access and – if this is feasible – license for reuse. Secondly, it should be considered whether the desire for various content categories is sufficiently covered by the current collecting of data, or if collecting data needs to be further improved.

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